

Investigation on strength and durability characteristics of ternary cementitious system using fly ash, lime and metakaolin

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Abstract

Advanced performance standards must be met by concrete structures in order to satisfy the expanding needs of contemporary construction. Additional cementitious materials (SCMs), such fly ash and metakaolin, can significantly enhance the mechanical performance, workability, and microstructural characteristics of ternary mixed concrete. This study focuses on investigating the effect of fly ash, metakaolin and lime powder on the mechanical and durability characteristics of concrete. The mechanical properties were assessed using compressive strength, split tensile strength, flexural strength, and durability was assessed through water permeability test, Rapid Chloride Permeability test. The results indicate that the mix composition MFL4, consisting of 20% metakaolin, 15% fly ash, and 5% limestone powder, demonstrated superior performance in terms of workability and mechanical strength. Compared to control concrete, the optimized mix exhibits enhanced strength characteristics and improved pore structure of the proposed ternary mix. This study highlights the potential usage of fly ash, lime and metakaolin to enhance the mechanical characteristics of concrete significantly and making it an effective solution for the modern construction demands.

Keywords

Ternary Blended Concrete, Metakaolin, Fly Ash, Mechanical Strength, Durability

1 Introduction

Concrete is a basic building material that is renowned for its durability and adaptability. Ternary Blended Concrete (TBC) is a major development in concrete technology that is intended to provide better mechanical qualities, increased longevity, and durability than traditional concrete. For important infrastructure projects where improved performance is crucial, it is especially beneficial [1]. Ternary Blended Concrete is a type of concrete that satisfies unique performance and consistency standards that aren't always possible with traditional ingredients, mixing, putting, and curing techniques. These specifications could enhance improvements such as long-term behavior, durability, workability, or mechanical qualities. In general, ternary blended concrete has a high cement content, a low water-

to-cement ratio, and the use of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as metakaolin, fly ash, and limestone powder. By strengthening resistance to chemical and environmental stresses, decreasing permeability, and improving the microstructure, these mineral admixtures enhance the qualities of concrete (Li et al., 2018).

The need for concrete structures to have better performance characteristics is what is driving the use of ternary blended concrete. According to some previous research, ternary mixes are essential for reducing the cement content of concrete while maintaining its high performance [3]. Supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as fly ash, silica fume, metakaolin, lime powder etc. work in unique combinations to produce improved mechanical qualities,

including increased flexural, tensile, and compressive strengths [4]. The combination of FA and silica fume (SF) significantly increases compressive strength, according to Nochaiya et al. [5] According to Zhao et al. (2015) [6], the addition of fly ash and ground granulated blast furnace slag to ternary mixed cement improves both flowability and compressive strength. Pozzolanic reactions that improve resistance to aggressive agents like sulphates and chlorides by reducing permeability and refining the pore structure are responsible for the increased durability [7]. Furthermore, fly ash particles' spherical shape improves workability by lowering internal friction and enhancing mix flowability without adding more water. Lime is a low-carbon substitute material that can be utilized in construction to improve sustainability. Lime powder also helps to achieve a consistency that is workable [8].

By lowering the heat of hydration and lowering the risk of thermal cracking in large structural elements, the addition of SCMs also offers thermal benefits. Additionally, using industrial byproducts like fly ash encourages environmentally friendly building methods, decreases carbon emissions, and lessens dependency on cement [9]. In addition to addressing environmental issues, this has financial benefits by reducing material costs without sacrificing performance. Along with fly ash (FA) and rice husk ash (RHA) as supplemental cementitious materials (SCM), oil palm shell (OPS) was used as coarse lightweight aggregate [10]. The construction industry's need for sustainable and high-performing materials is what led to the development of Ternary Blended Concrete. Given that the production of cement contributes significantly to global CO₂ emissions, environmental responsibility is essential [11, 12]. The carbon footprint can be decreased by replacing some of the cement with

SCMs like fly ash, metakaolin, and lime powder. Waste utilization is another important factor because it promotes waste recycling and a circular economy by using materials like fly ash, wood waste ash that would otherwise end up in landfills to make concrete [13, 14, 15] reported that higher compressive strength is achieved by combining cement, fly ash, and egg shell powder in proportions of 70%, 20%, and 10%, respectively as part of ternary blended concrete.

Enhanced infrastructure performance is essential, especially with structures expected to last longer and withstand harsher conditions. By incorporating SCMs such as metakaolin, fly ash, silica fume Ternary Blended Concrete achieves superior mechanical properties, enhanced durability, and sustainability, making it an ideal choice for modern construction needs [16]. When compared to traditional binary blended cements or ordinary Portland cement, ternary blended cements have been shown in recent years to significantly enhance the performance of concrete [17]. Ternary Blended Concrete meets these performance requirements, ensuring durability and strength [18]. The fundamental concept underlying the development of ternary mixes is that more particles will be packed together during production, which could result in uniform nucleation and the creation of hydration products with intense microstructure [20, 41]. Consequently, binders with increased strength and durability would be produced. Additionally, regulatory compliance with stricter environmental regulations is facilitated by incorporating SCMs, helping meet sustainability and environmental impact standards [21, 22]. This study focuses on the experimental investigation of metakaolin-based Ternary Blended Concrete. Metakaolin, a highly reactive pozzolanic material derived from kaolin clay, is used as a partial replacement for cement in the concrete mix and MK enhances the durability, mechanical qualities, and workability of concrete [23, 32].

Prasanna Kumar et al. [24] concluded that inclusion of Lime up to 7% resulting in

remarkable strength improvement in all tested ages. El-Alfi [25] identified that the consumption of calcite in the concrete mix leads to the acceleration of the hydration of C_3A and C_3S compounds, the alteration of the C–S–H gel and the creation of a transition zone between the cement paste and the filler. Based on these facts it was proposed to keep 5% Lime content in weight percentage of cement to be a supplementary cementitious component in this study.

The literature indicates that very few studies have addressed the combined use of fly ash, lime, and metakaolin in the creation of a ternary binder that is environmentally benign. Hence, the objective of this research is to produce a ternary blend of binder materials by utilizing fly ash waste as the base material and combining it with high alkaline materials like lime, metakaolin as additives. By understanding the effects of metakaolin, this research seeks to optimize concrete mix designs for advanced construction applications, offering more durable and resilient structures.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Fine Aggregate

Fine aggregate of fineness modulus of 2.8–3.0, satisfying the IS: 383 standard code provisions of the zone-II sand were used as fine aggregate in this study. Manufactured sand (M-sand), exhibiting comparable strength to natural sand with controlled particle size was used as fine aggregate.

2.1.2 Coarse Aggregate

Cubical-shaped coarse aggregate satisfying the requirements of IS: 383 standard code provisions were used as coarse aggregate in this study. The maximum particle size of the coarse aggregate is limited to 20 mm to achieve higher compressive strength in concrete.

Properties of fine aggregate and coarse aggregate are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Properties of fine aggregate and coarse aggregate

Property	Fine Aggregate	Coarse Aggregate
Fineness	2.58	6.8
Modulus		
Specific Gravity	2.63	2.8
Water	-	1%
Absorption		

2.1.3. Cement

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) of 53 grade and conforms to the specifications of IS 12269:1987, was utilized as the primary binding material in this study. The physical properties such as fineness, setting time, and compressive strength were tested according to IS 4031 standards.

2.1.4 Fly Ash

Fly ash obtained from the Tuticorin power plant was used in the development of ternary blended concrete. This study utilized Type F fly ash, which primarily undergoes pozzolanic reactions due to its low calcium oxide (CaO) content. Typically, Type F fly ash replaces cement in volume ratios of 10%–30%. Its spherical particle shape enhances the workability of the concrete mix by reducing inter-particle friction. Despite the fact that fly ash's lower hydration reactivity slows down the hydration process and lowers early-age mechanical strengths, the slower pozzolanic reaction gradually improves the microstructure's strength and durability over time.

2.1.5 Metakaolin

Metakaolin is a highly effective pozzolan and is frequently used as a constituent in ternary blended concrete mixtures. Typically, metakaolin is used to replace cement in the range of 5% to 20% by weight. Prior research on concrete with 5–20 weight percent MK addition revealed a 70–

90% drop in the concrete mixes' performance indices [26, 31].

The addition of metakaolin increases the particle packing density and improves the workability of the concrete because of its fine particle size and high reactivity. The pozzolanic activity of metakaolin, which is enhanced by its high alumina and silica content, reacts with calcium hydroxide to produce more calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H), improving the concrete's microstructure. Because metakaolin reduces permeability and refines the pore structure, it improves the durability of ternary blended concrete and increases its mechanical strengths.

2.1.6 Limestone Powder

For ternary blended concrete, limestone powder has been suggested as a substitute kind of micro filler. Up to 50% of the volume can be made up of cement replacement. Like quartz powder, the particle size of limestone powder is between 10 and 20 μm . The addition of limestone powder improves the workability of ternary blended concrete because of its small particle size, spherical shape, and inert property.

In addition to reducing autogenous shrinkage, the use of limestone powder speeds up the hydration reaction. The filler effect prevents limestone powder from hydrating, but it does offer additional nucleation sites for cement and/or other reactive particles to hydrate. Furthermore, the dilution effect of substituting limestone powder for cement raises the effective water-to-cement ratio, provides more free water for cement hydration, and helps to maintain the internal relative humidity (IRH). The cementitious admixtures of the proposed Ternary Blended Concrete (TBC) are displayed in Figure 1 and the properties are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 1 Cementitious admixtures of TBC

Table 2 Properties of cementitious materials

Property	Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC)	Metakaolin (MK)	Fly Ash (FA)	Lime Powder (LP)
SiO ₂ Content (%)	21	52.5	47.5	3
Al ₂ O ₃ Content (%)	6	42.5	22.5	1.25
Fe ₂ O ₃ Content (%)	4	2	7	1.25
CaO Content (%)	62.5	1	5.5	52.5
MgO Content (%)	2.25	0.5	1.75	1.75
Loss on Ignition (%)	3	1	5	2

2.1.7 Mix Proportion

Mix proportioning was carried out adhering to the guidelines provided in the Indian Standard Code IS 10262-2019 concrete mix design. Table 3 describes the mix proportion.

Table 3 Mix Proportion (M-40Grade)

Cement	Fine aggregate	Coarse aggregate	Water
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1	1.07	1.44	0.3
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2.1.8 Mix Specification

The ternary blended concrete (TBC) mixes were developed using Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) as the primary binder, partially replaced with metakaolin, fly ash, and limestone powder in varying proportions. Fine aggregate utilized was manufactured sand (M-sand) with a fineness modulus of 2.8, meeting the requirements of Zone II as per IS: 383. Coarse aggregate with a maximum size of 20 mm was incorporated. Water-binder ratio (w/b) was optimized to balance workability and strength. Chemical admixtures such as super plasticizers were used to enhance flow ability. The inclusion of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) in the mix design was tailored to improve mechanical properties and to refine microstructural characteristics and achieving better durability of concrete. Table 4 presents the appropriate quantities of cement, aggregates, and supplementary materials such as metakaolin, fly ash and lime powder of the proposed TBC.

Table 4 Mix Specification of the Ternary Blended Concrete

Mix ID	Cement in kg/m ³	FA in kg/m ³	CA in kg/m ³	Fly Ash in kg/m ³	LP in kg/m ³	MK in kg/m ³
MFL 1	438.4	642.7	864.7	90	30	42.05
MFL 2	420.4	642.7	864.7	90	30	60.07
MFL 3	390.4	642.7	864.7	90	30	90.10
MFL 4	360.4	642.7	864.7	90	30	120.1
MFL 5	330.3	642.7	864.7	90	30	150.1

3. Methods

The mechanical strength characteristics of Ternary Blended Concrete (TBC) were evaluated following IS 516 [27], including compressive, split tensile and flexural tests. Chloride permeability was tested as per ASTM C1202-10 [28], measuring the resistance of concrete to chloride ion penetration. Water permeability was assessed in accordance with IS 3085 [29], where specimens were subjected to water pressure to determine penetration depth. Additionally, the pore structure of the concrete was evaluated following ASTM C1585, which measures the rate of water absorption by hydraulic-cement concrete to analyze the microstructural impact of SCMs on the concrete matrix. This comprehensive methodology ensured a detailed assessment of the mechanical and microstructural properties of TBC. As illustrated in Figure 1A to 1F, various tests have been conducted in this investigation.

3.1 Workability Tests

3.1.1 Slump Cone Test

Concrete consistency is most typically measured using the slump test, which can be conducted in a lab or on a construction site. It does not measure every factor that influences workability and is not always a reliable indicator of the concrete's place ability. It shows not just the slump value but also the properties of the concrete. It is referred to be true slump if the concrete slumps uniformly. When one side of the cone slips downward, shear slump occurs. The height difference between the mould's height and an average subsidence value is used for determining the slump. As illustrated in Figure 2a, the slump cone test used in this investigation to find the consistency of concrete.

3.1.2 Compaction Factor

When determining whether concrete is workable, especially for mixes with limited workability, the compaction factor test plays vital role. A compaction factor apparatus with two conical hoppers and a bottom cylinder is utilized

for the test. Following its placement in the upper hopper, a trapdoor is opened to allow the concrete flow into the lower hopper. This procedure is repeated to move the partially compacted concrete into the cylinder, followed by rodding to complete the compacting process. Weighing the cylinders holding partially and fully compacted concrete is necessary to determine the compaction factor. The degree of workability is indicated by this value; greater values indicate better workability. Figure 2b, illustrates the compaction factor test to evaluate workability in this study.

Fig. 2 Workability Tests on TBC

3.2 Strength Tests

3.2.1 Compression Testing

Indian Standards state that the characteristic compressive strength of 150 mm size cubes measured at 28 days (f_{ck}) is used to determine the compressive strength of concrete. Compressive strength is calculated by dividing the load by the specimen's area. The concrete's typical strength is the strength below which not more than 5% of test results are anticipated to drop. A value higher than the mix design value should be found in 95% of the tested cubes. This is the characteristic strength of concrete, which is the strength of concrete specimens cast, tested, and cured for 28 days in accordance with the specified code of practice. Figure 3a displays the compression testing configuration used in this investigation.

3.2.2 Split Tensile Testing

Concrete's capacity to withstand tension is gauged by its split tensile strength. In accordance

with the standards established by pertinent codes of practice, it is ascertained by testing cylindrical specimens of concrete, typically measuring 150 mm in diameter (D) and 300 mm in height (L). Tensile stresses perpendicular to the loading direction are induced by applying a diametric compressive force over the length of a cylindrical specimen. The specimen splits along the diameter as a result. The split tensile strength is then computed using the specimen's maximum load (P) before failure. This test is crucial for comprehending how concrete behaves under tensile loads, which are important in situations like failure mechanisms and cracking. Figure 3b shows the split tensile strength testing setup.

$$\text{Split tensile strength} = (2P)/\pi DL$$

Where P- Load in N

D – Diameter of the specimen

L – Length of the specimen

3.2.3 Flexural Strength Testing

The flexural strength of concrete is a measure of its ability to resist bending or flexural loads. For structures like beams and slabs that are subjected to bending loads, this feature is crucial. Concrete beam specimens, usually measuring 100mm x 100mm x 500mm, are tested for flexural strength in accordance with applicable norms of practice. In order to create a bending moment, a load is applied to the center of the beam specimen while it is supported at both ends. The greatest load (P) that the specimen can withstand before failing is then used to compute the flexural strength. Figure 3c depicts the flexural strength testing apparatus utilized in this investigation.

$$\text{Flexural Strength, } f_b = 3PL/(2bd^2)$$

Where P- Load in N

D – Diameter of the specimen

b – Breadth of the specimen

d – Depth of the specimen

3.3 Durability Studies

3.3.1 Rapid Chloride Permeability Test

The RCPT specifically outlined in standards like ASTM C 1202, [28] is a widely adopted method to evaluate how effectively concrete resists the penetration of chloride ions. This test is crucial because chloride ingress can lead to corrosion of reinforcing steel within concrete,

significantly reducing the lifespan of structures. A concrete specimen is exposed to a steady electrical voltage for six hours in order for the RCPT to function. During this period, the current passing through the concrete is meticulously measured, and the total electrical charge passed is calculated in coulombs. A higher coulomb value indicates that more chloride ions have passed through the concrete, signifying higher permeability and consequently, lower resistance to chloride penetration.

This rapid and straightforward test serves as an essential quality control tool, allowing engineers to assess the electrical conductance of various concrete mixes and predict the long-term performance and service life of concrete structures in environments exposed to chlorides. Figure 3d describes Rapid Chloride Permeability Test (RCPT) set up.

3.3.2 Water Permeability Test

Water permeability is a critical property of concrete that determines its ability to resist the passage of water through its pores. High permeability can lead to the ingress of harmful substances, such as chlorides and sulphates, which can cause deterioration of concrete and corrosion of reinforcement. The water permeability test measures the rate at which water penetrates through concrete under a specified pressure, providing valuable information about the concrete's durability and quality. The test is conducted by subjecting concrete specimens to water pressure and measuring the amount of water that passes through the specimen over a given period. Lower permeability values indicate better resistance to water ingress and higher durability. The test setup for water permeability is shown in Figure 3e.

$$k = (Q.L)/(A.t.h)$$

Where

k = Coefficient of permeability (cm/sec)

Q = Volume of water passing through the specimen (cm³)

L = Thickness of the specimen (cm)

A = Cross-sectional area exposed to water flow (cm²)

t = Time duration of water flow (seconds)

h = Hydraulic head or pressure applied (cm)

3.3.3 Pore Structure Determination

Three essential parameters - saturated water absorption (SWA), porosity, and Sorptivity - were used to describe the concrete's pore structure. SWA determines how much water is absorbed when the material is fully saturated, giving information about its density and permeability. The volume of vacant spaces in the concrete matrix is measured by porosity, which has a direct impact on the material's strength and longevity. The microstructural behavior and water-ingress resistance of concrete are evaluated by Sorptivity, which measures the rate of water absorption by capillary action. When taken as a whole, these metrics provide a thorough understanding of the pore structure and aid in evaluating the overall durability and performance of the concrete.

3.3.3.1 Sorptivity Test

The Sorptivity Test calculates how quickly water is absorbed into concrete through capillary action. This test is essential for assessing concrete's durability since it reveals information about the material's pore structure and water-resistance. As presented in Figure 3f, a concrete specimen is exposed to water during the test, and the mass increase caused by water absorption is tracked over time. The rate of absorption is calculated and expressed using sorptivity, a measurement of the concrete's capacity to absorb and transmit water through capillarity. Greater durability and improved resistance to water intrusion are indicated by lower Sorptivity levels.

$$S = (Wc - Wd) / [(A \cdot \rho \cdot t)]^{0.5}$$

Where,

Wc = dry weight of the cylinder in grams

Wd = weight of the cylinder after capillary suction in grams

A = surface area of the cylinder exposed to water penetration by capillary action in mm²

ρ = density of water

t = time in minutes after conducting completely immersed

Figure. 3a to 3f: 3a - Compression testing 3b - Split tension testing 3c - Flexural strength testing 3d - Rapid chloride permeability test 3e - Water permeability test 3f - Sorptivity test

4 Results and discussions

4.1 Tests on fresh concrete

Table 5 Workability test results

MIX ID	Slump value in mm	Compaction factor
CC	100 mm	1.03
MFL1	98 mm	0.97
MFL2	96 mm	0.95
MFL3	93 mm	0.94
MFL4	91 mm	0.91
MFL5	90 mm	0.90

Table 5 displays the slump cone test and compaction factor test results to assess the workability of all mixes tested. Results show that both control concrete and MFL mixes show reasonably good workability in both of the observed workability indices. It was found that the inclusion of metakaolin and lime decreases the workability due to the presence of finer particles and the denser packing of the mixes. Also, the variation between CC and MFL lies between 2% to 10% in case of slump values and the compaction factor varies between 6% to 12%. However the observed workability indices ensure the

suitability of the MFL mixes for the structural concrete applications. It was also observed that none of the MFL mixes showed any bleeding.

4.2 Tests on hardened concrete

4.2.1 Compressive strength of concrete

The compressive strength of the MFL mixes (MFL1 to MFL5) shows a notable improvement over conventional concrete (CC) across 7, 14, and 28 days strength achievement. The comparison displayed in Figure 4 shows that all MFL mixes achieved higher early-age compressive strength compared to CC. MFL4 performed the best, achieving 54.5% higher strength at 7 days, demonstrating the effectiveness of SCMs in enhancing early-age performance. In comparison to Control concrete, MFL4, which performed the best, has shown a remarkable increase in compressive strength. At 7, 14, and 28 days, MFL4 outperformed Control concrete with compressive strengths that were 54.5%, 31.8%, and 29.7% greater, respectively. Due to the filler effect, and the pozzolanic reaction of MK with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ which forms more C-S-H gel, and the

particle shape of Metakaolin reveal that MK will enhance the strength and durability performance of concrete [33, 34]. Overall, the results show that SCMs significantly increase the compressive strength of concrete which with MFL4 being the mix for obtaining the remarkable strength improvement at all tested ages.

Fig. 4 Compressive Strength Test Results

4.2.2 Split Tensile Strength of Concrete

As illustrated in Figure 5, analogous to the compressive strength observation the MFL mixes (MFL1 to MFL5) demonstrates a notable improvement in split tensile strength observations compared to control concrete (CC). Comparing the MFL4 mix to the Control Concrete specimens, the MFL4 mix demonstrated superior

performance by achieving 85%, 75%, and 73.3% higher split tensile strength at 7, 14, and 28 days, respectively. MK particles have a platy, angular shape with a noticeable level of roughness on their surface [35]. This particle shape may attribute the close association within the cementitious matrix and dense packing of mixes which marks the notable split tensile strength of the MFL series of mixes.

Fig. 5 Split Tensile Strength Test Results

4.2.3 Flexural Strength of Concrete

Flexural strength test results are displayed in Figure 6, which shows that comparative observations of flexural strength of the MFL mixes shows the significant role of metakaolin and lime to contribute the strength gain of the MFL mixes. MFL4 mix achieved 75%, 61.3%, and 43.1% higher flexural strengths than the concrete at 7, 14, and 28 days, respectively confirming the optimized values of 15% fly ash, 5% Lime and 15% Metakaolin as supplementary cementitious materials in weight percentage of cement in Ternary Blended concrete which is in good correlation with the results obtained by Habeeb, 2018.

Metakaolin is well known for its beneficial effects on enhancing concrete performance. By interacting with accessible calcium hydroxide/portlandite to produce secondary calcium silica hydrate (C-S-H) and many other hydrates (C_3AH_6 , and C_2ASH_8 or stratlingite) [36]. It is observed that MFL4 mix with 15% Fly Ash, 5% Lime and 15% Metakaolin as supplementary cementitious materials emerging

as the most effective mix for achieving superior strength in the tested MFL mix series.

Figure. 6 Flexural Strength Test Results

4.2.4 Water Permeability

The permeability test results presented in Figure 7, reveal that the water permeability of the samples improved progressively from conventional concrete (CC) to the SCM-enhanced mixes, with the MFL5 mix exhibiting the lowest permeability value of 0.268. This improvement is attributed to the synergistic effects of metakaolin, fly ash, and limestone powder, which refine the pore structure and reduce capillary porosity.

Particles of SCM such as metakaolin, flyash, silicafume can exhibit the micro aggregate effect by filling up the spaces between cementitious material particles in the microstructure, the ITZ defect, and other micro void structures [37]. In contrast, conventional concrete demonstrated the highest permeability at 0.355, indicating a less dense microstructure. The gradual decrease in permeability values from MFL1 to MFL5 highlights the effectiveness of optimized blends in enhancing impermeability, making TBC a suitable choice for applications requiring durable and low-permeability materials.

Fig. 7 Water Permeability Test Results

4.2.5 Rapid Chloride Permeability Test

The chloride permeability results, conducted as per ASTM C1202 and Table 6 describe the ranking of Chloride Ion Penetrability as per the standards and Table 7 show distinct variations among the mixes, highlighting the impact of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) on concrete performance based on the RCPT

observations. The conventional concrete (CC) exhibited a charge passed of 657 coulombs, indicating very low permeability and superior resistance to chloride ion ingress. In comparison, mixes incorporating SCMs, such as MFL1, MFL2, MFL3, MFL4, and MFL5, demonstrated progressively increasing charge values, ranging from 875 to 1105 coulombs, categorizing them as having low permeability.

This increment suggests that while the addition of metakaolin, fly ash, and limestone powder enhances certain mechanical and durability properties, it may slightly increase the chloride permeability in comparison to the control mix. Many studies have been conducted on how SCMs affect the flow of chloride ions and compact the pore structure. Li et al. 2015 [38] reported that based on Rapid Chloride Permeability Test (RCPT) and Rapid Chloride Migration (RCM) test, addition of metakaolin in cementitious mixtures improved the concrete's resistance to chloride by means of improving the pore structure as well as immobilization of the chloride by metakaolin.

Table 6 Ranking of Chloride Ion Penetrability (ASTM C1202-12 [28]).

Rapid Chloride Ion Permeability	Charge Passed (Columbs)
High	> 4000
Moderate	2000- 4000
Low	1000 - 2000
Very Low	100 - 1000
Negligible	< 100

Table 7 Rapid Chloride Permeability Test Results

MIX ID	Charge passed in 6 hours	Chloride Permeability
CC	757	Very Low

MFL 1	875	Very Low
MFL 2	950	Very Low
MFL 3	1010	Low
MFL 4	1028	Low
MFL 5	1105	Low

Among the modified blends, MFL5 showed the highest charge passed (1105 coulombs), which, while still within the low permeability range, indicates a trade-off between optimizing mechanical performance and maintaining chloride resistance. These findings emphasize the need to balance SCM proportions to achieve desired performance metrics for specific construction applications.

4.2.6 Pore Structure Determination

Figure 8, 9 and 10 explained the schematic representation of the pore structure observations. The results demonstrate a clear improvement in the pore structure characteristics from conventional concrete (CC) to the ternary blended concrete mixes (MFL1 to MFL5). Saturated water absorption (SWA) decreased significantly from 1.132% in CC to 0.617% in MFL5, indicating reduced permeability and a denser matrix in the modified mixes. Porosity also showed a progressive decline, reducing from 0.070 in CC to 0.036 in MFL5, which reflects effective pore refinement due to the addition of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs). Similarly, sorptivity values reduced from 0.0064 cm/sec^{1/2} in CC to 0.0033 cm/sec^{1/2} in MFL5, highlighting enhanced resistance to water ingress through capillary action. These trends emphasize the substantial role of SCMs in improving durability and water resistance by modifying the microstructure of the concrete [40].

Cementitious materials treated with supplementary materials exhibit improved performance primarily due to filler effect, pozzolanic reactions, ITZ optimization, and densification of the cementitious matrix [41, 42].

Overall, the results validate the effectiveness of the ternary blended concrete in achieving superior performance compared to conventional concrete

Fig. 8 Saturated Water Absorption Test Results

Fig. 9 Porosity Test Results

Fig. 10 Sorptivity Test Results

5 Conclusions

This study establishes the efficacy of ternary blended concrete (TBC) incorporating supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as metakaolin, fly ash, and limestone powder in enhancing mechanical and durability properties. The mechanical strength evaluations reveal that the 20% replacement of metakaolin yielded the highest compressive, tensile, and flexural strengths, demonstrating the potential of

optimized SCM proportions to significantly improve concrete performance. Durability assessments, including water permeability and rapid chloride permeability tests (RCPT), confirmed the profound influence of SCMs in refining microstructural characteristics. Additionally, pore structure parameters such as saturated water absorption (SWA), porosity, and sorptivity evidenced a significant refinement in microstructure [43, 44]. Eventually, the incorporation of Fly ash, Lime and Metakaolin as supplementary cementitious materials in the proposed ternary blended concrete resulting into effective densification leading to improved impermeability and durability. In conclusion, the findings underscore the viability of ternary blended concrete as a high-performance and sustainable solution for modern construction. Optimized use of SCMs enhances both mechanical and durability metrics, making TBC a suitable choice for applications demanding superior performance. Future research could focus on balancing chloride permeability and strength enhancements to achieve further optimization for specialized applications.

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